

Occupational exposure limits for reproductive toxicants – A comparative analysis

Linda Schenk^{a,*}, Meng-Rung Ho^a, Piia Taxell^b, Pasi Huuskonen^b, Mimmi Leite^c, Inese Martinsone^d, Karl-Christian Nordby^c, Linda Paegle^d, Loreta Strumylaite^e

^a Integrative Toxicology, Institute of Environmental Medicine, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

^b Finnish Institute of Occupational Health, Helsinki, Finland

^c National Institute of Occupational Health in Norway, Oslo, Norway

^d Institute of Occupational Safety and Environmental Health, Riga Stradiņš University, Riga, Latvia

^e Neuroscience Institute, Medical Academy, Lithuanian University of Health Sciences, Kaunas, Lithuania

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ABSTRACT

We investigated the level of protection of reproductive and developmental toxicity offered through occupational exposure limits (OELs) and Derived No-Effect Levels for workers' inhalation exposure (wDNELs). We compared coverage of substances that have a harmonised classification as reproductive toxicant 1A or 1B (Repr.1A/B), numerical values and scientific basis of 12 lists of OELs and wDNELs from REACH Registrants' and the Committee for Risk Assessment. Across the 14 sources of OELs and wDNELs, 53% of the Repr1A/B-substances had at least one exposure limit (counting groups of metals as one entry). Registrants' wDNELs covered the largest share, 40%. The numerical values could be highly variable for the same substance across the lists. How often reproductive toxicity is identified as the critical effect varies between the examined lists, both due to different assessments of the same substance and different substance coverage. Reviewing the margin of safety to reproductive toxicity cited in the documents, we found that 15% of safety margins were lower to reproductive toxicity than the critical effect. To conclude, neither the REACH nor work environment legislation supply wDNELs or OELs for a substantial share of known reproductive toxicants. EU OELs cover among the fewest substances in the range, and in many cases national OELs or wDNELs are set at more conservative levels.

1. Introduction

With the changes in workforce demographics and work life organization new challenges arise to work environment and chemical regulations as well as health risk assessments under these. There have been concerns that the current work environment legislation and the body of research underpinning it implicitly holds the healthy male worker as the norm [1-4]. A consequence of such an undeclared norm could be that women, including pregnant women, are less protected than men.

Indeed, pregnant and breastfeeding workers are in some cases specifically targeted by a separate set of regulations requiring an additional layer of protective measures for these subpopulations. Within the European Union (EU) this is exemplified by the "Pregnant Workers Directive" [5]. It has been argued that such a differentiated protection strategy is inefficient and may also exacerbate discrimination of women in the workplace [1,6].

Calls for further reform in the regulatory framework are fuelled by an increasing number of studies showing how chemicals may interfere with

Abbreviations: BOELV, Binding Occupational Exposure Limit Value; CAS, Chemical Abstracts Service; CLP, Regulation EC No 1272/2008 on the classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures; CMRD, Carcinogens, Mutagens or Reprotoxic substances Directive 2004/37/EC; DNEL, Derived No-Effect Level; DMEL, Derived Minimal-Effect Level; ECHA, European Chemicals Agency; EU, European Union; IOELV, Indicative Occupational Exposure Limit Value; MAK Commission, Senate Commission for the Investigation of Health Hazards of Chemical Compounds in the Work Area; OEL, Occupational Exposure Limit; PoD, Point of departure; REACH, Regulation on the registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals; RAC, ECHA's Committee for Risk Assessment; SCOEL, Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits; TWA, Time-weighted average; wDNEL, DNEL for workers' long-term inhalation exposure; wDMEL, DMEL for workers' long-term inhalation exposure.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: linda.schenk@ki.se (L. Schenk).

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our reproductive function. Heavy metals, for example, can impact the menstrual cycle and cause spontaneous abortion [7,8] and impair sperm parameters [9,10]. Moreover, prenatal exposure to bisphenol A is suggested to be connected with fertility effects in the subsequent generations [11]. Evidence from mechanistic studies demonstrate that certain chemicals could exert the reproductive effects through disrupting the homeostasis of sex steroid hormones [12]. Endocrine disruption has also been suggested as one potential area where a non-threshold paradigm may apply to reproductive toxicity [13].

While “pregnant women have been the starting point for studies of reproductive hazards” (as phrased by [3], all kinds of reproductive toxicity have recently come into focus as the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive [14] was expanded in 2022 as the fourth amendment added reproductive toxicants to the scope of the directive (now CMRD). With this amendment to CMRD [15], 11 EU indicative occupational exposure limit values (IOELVs) for substances with a harmonised classification [16] as toxic to reproduction category 1A or 1B were transferred to binding occupational exposure limit values (BOELVs). IOELVs are derived for substances whose critical effect is shown (or presumed) to have a threshold mechanism of action. A majority of reproductive toxicants are considered to have an effect threshold [17], although it has been opened up for discussion that some reproductive toxicants may act through a non-threshold mode of action [13]. The CMRD originally was tailored for non-threshold acting substances. Hence, the CMRD also requires that potential non-threshold mechanisms of reproductive toxicants need to be identified.

Part of the substances that fall or may come to fall under CMRD are already regulated by the Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) [18]. Under REACH, an exposure guidance value called derived no-effect level (DNEL) is to be derived for threshold acting substances, and a derived minimal-effect level (DMEL) for non-threshold acting ones. The DNELs and DMELs derived for workers’ long term inhalation exposure (wDNEL) are very similar in nature to OELs, as they define concentrations in inhalation air with the aim to protect workers’ health. The wDNELs are mainly derived by REACH registrants, that is the manufacturers and importers of chemical substances within the EU. The REACH regulation enables restriction of occupational exposure to chemicals when certain conditions are met. The means of restriction are not described in detail in the regulation, but harmonised DNELs can be one of them. These are derived by the Risk Assessment Committee of ECHA (RAC), who may also set DNELs to be used as reference levels for evaluating the adequacy of authorisation conditions. Hence, in a few limited cases, RAC derives wDNELs that the European Commission may adopt through REACH Restriction or Authorisation decisions.

There are substantial differences between wDNELs and OELs, such as their intended use, actors involved, substance selection criteria, and procedure of derivation. OELs are generally based on a scientific evaluation from an independent expert group; in the case of EU level OELs, the responsibility shifted from the Scientific Committee on OELs (SCOEL) to RAC. But there are also many national as well as other organisations involved in making OEL recommendations. It should also be noted that not all OELs are strictly health-based; in some cases, such as the EU binding OELs, socioeconomic factors are taken into account in their setting. REACH defines wDNELs a health-based value, but the regulation does not define a risk target for wDMELs (i.e. for non-threshold effects). A previous comparison of coverage and derivations methods between wDNELs and OELs concluded that wDNELs extend the landscape beyond OELs in terms of substance coverage but that there are some concerns regarding their scientific basis [19].

The present study investigates the level of protection the work environment legislation and REACH offers towards reproductive and developmental toxicity through occupational exposure limits. This aim is addressed through mapping and comparing the coverage, the numerical values and the scientific basis of OELs and wDNELs for reproductive toxicants.

2. Methods

The present study is based on comparisons across 12 lists of European OELs or OEL recommendations and wDNELs from ECHA Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) and REACH Registrants (Table 1). For each source we searched for a methodology document for the OEL derivation or, if not available, a description of the OELs’ protective aims in the list of OELs or associated regulation. These documents were searched for any specific policy towards reproductive toxicants. If no mention of reproductive toxicity, offspring or pregnancy was found, a statement reflecting the protection aim was selected instead. In addition, for each list, 8 h time-weighted average (TWA) OELs and long-term wDNELs were tabulated if available for substances with a harmonised classification as reproductive toxicants (Repr.) in categories 1A or 1B up until the 18th Adaptation to Technical Progress (ATP18) of the classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) regulation [16]. Substance identification was mainly based on CAS-number. In the case of metals and metal compounds, the substance name and physicochemical properties were used for identification as most OEL lists define one OEL for a

Table 1

Lists of occupational exposure limits and derived no-effect levels included in the present study, with references to lists and scientific documentation. Data was extracted in early 2023.

List	References	
	Values	Scientific documents
EU BOELV	[14] as amended up until [15]	RAC and SCOEL (see below)
RAC OEL rec SCOEL rec	https://echa.europa.eu/oels-activity-list https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=148&langId=en&intPagelId=684	
Registrant’s wDNELs RAC wDNELs	https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals/registered-substances https://echa.europa.eu/sv/registry-of-restriction-intentions https://echa.europa.eu/sv/applying-for-authorisation/evaluating-applications	
Finland	https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/handle/10024/162457	https://tyosuojelu.fi/tyoolot/kemiallis-et-tekijat/raja-arvot/perustelumuiot https://www.anses.fr/fr/content/les-valeurs-de-reference https://www.healthcouncil.nl/documents
France	https://www.inrs.fr/publications/bdd/vlep.html	
Netherlands	https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0008587/2024-01-01/#BijlageXIII	
Latvia	https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/157382-labour-protection-requirements-when-coming-in-contact-with-chemical-substances-at-workplaces	Generally based on other OEL documents
Lithuania	https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/legalAct.html?documentId=TAR.8012ED3EA143	Generally based on other OEL documents
MAK Commission	https://onlinelibrary-wiley-com.proxy.kib.ki.se/page/book/10.1002/3527600418/homepage/access_to_the_list_of_mak_and_bat_values.htm	Retrievable: https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/book/10.1002/3527600418
Norway	https://www.arbeidstilsynet.no/regelverk/forskrifter/forskrift-om-tiltaks-og-grenseverdier/vedlegg/1/	https://www.arbeidstilsynet.no/tema/kjemikalier/grenseverdier-for-kjemisk-pavirking/grunnlagsdokumenter-for-grenseverdier-for-kjemikalier/
Spain	https://www.insst.es/presentacion_dlep	https://www.insst.es/dlep-documentacion-toxicologica
Sweden	https://www.av.se/arbetsmiljoarbete-och-inspektioner/publikationer/foreskrifter/hygieniska-gransvarden-afs-20181-foreskrifter/	Published in the series Arbete och Hälsa (ISSN 0346-7821)

group of metal compounds, many times with a delimitation such as “inorganic” or “soluble” metal compounds. Since OELs for metal compounds are generally set as a concentration of the metal in question, any wDNELs derived for the specific metal compound were recalculated to corresponding amount of metal.

We tabulated OELs and wDNELs in the unit mg/m^3 , and if necessary recalculated values only given as ppm to mg/m^3 assuming 20°C and 101kPa. For particulates, the OEL for the inhalable fraction was preferred if an OEL for more than one particle fraction was available. In the case of nickel compounds, the tabulated Swedish OEL is set for the previously used particle fraction “total dust”, other tabulated OELs and wDNELs were derived for inhalable dust. A correction factor of 2 was used to make the Swedish OEL comparable to the inhalable dust OELs [20]. In instances the registrants assumed a non-threshold mode of action and calculated a wDMEL rather than a wDNEL, we extracted and tabulated the value in the same manner.

When available, we retrieved the scientific documents outlining the OEL or DNEL derivation in order to extract information on the critical effects, i.e., the health effects underlying the OELs and DNELs. The critical effects were categorised as reproductive toxicity, carcinogenicity, other systemic toxicity or local toxicity.

For EU level exposure limits (top 5 entries in Table 1) we extracted additional information on the derivation procedure for the OELs and wDNELs. Specifically, we extracted the following information:

- key study for the critical effect,
- point of departure (PoD) for the OEL/wDNEL,
- assessment factors (or if not specified safety margin, i.e., OEL/PoD),
- conclusion about reproductive toxicity,
- range of all dose-descriptors cited for reproductive toxicity.

The point of departure was divided by the OEL/wDNEL to calculate the implicit safety margin for the critical effect. Similarly, the range of dose-descriptors for reproductive toxicity was used to calculate a document specific, implicit safety margin to reproductive toxicity. For this we used the lowest cited dose-descriptor in each document.

3. Results

We were not able to find clear statements on the protective aims regarding reproductive toxicity for all of the included OEL lists (Table 2). The protective aims identified varied somewhat in phrasing, e.g. workers and their offspring or workers and their reproductive health. The statements not specifically indicating a policy to include reproductive toxicity, yet connected to the protective aims of reproductive toxicity ranged from the definition of the OELs to be set specifically for reproductive toxicants (EU BOELVs) to the derivation procedure should include data on reproductive toxicity (e.g. wDNELs, Norway), to statements outlining caveats due to the lack of reliable empirical data and statements. The most specific and transparent approach to reproductive toxicity is the MAK commission’s notation on pregnancy risk groups. These notations offer users a simple overview of the state of knowledge, and if the recommended OEL can be expected to protect the embryo or foetus (Table 2). It can be noted that national, legally binding OELs generally allow for (but may not require) inclusion of socioeconomic considerations in the determination of the final value, as does BOELVs. However, the BOELVs included in this study were directly transferred from health-based IOELVs. Recommendations from the MAK-commission, ECHA RAC and SCOEL or wDNELs are considered health-based, that is not considering socio-economic feasibility.

By CAS numbers, more than 250 substances have a harmonised classification as toxic to reproduction category 1 A or 1B (up to ATP18 of 1272/2008/EC). Table 3 outlines the coverage across the selected lists of exposure limits for these substances. It is noteworthy that a substantial amount of the classified substances belongs to the group of nickel compounds. There is also a difference regarding whether an OEL list

specifies the OEL as “nickel and its compounds” or the more narrow “nickel and its inorganic compounds”. This is the major reason for the differences in counts between BOELVs and SCOEL recommendations in Table 3. Hence, in Table 3 we separate the coverage including all CAS numbers for metal compounds and the coverage when excluding multiple substances from groups of metals. The largest coverage in the latter case is then found for Registrant’s wDNELs at 40 %, while national and the EU OEL lists cover 8–16 %. ECHA RAC, which is the most recent OEL actor listed in Table 3, has published the fewest recommendations as of yet. Across all substances 68 % have a OEL or wDNEL from at least one of the sources listed in Table 3 (53 % excluding the individual metal compounds).

The most frequently listed substances are: bisphenol A, carbon monoxide, N,N-dimethylacetamide and N,N-dimethylformamide, 2-ethoxy ethanol, lead compounds, 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone and nickel compounds. This excludes frequently evaluated non-threshold carcinogens that do not receive numerical recommendations by all actors included.

In Fig. 1 we compare the numerical values of the OELs to those of Registrant’s wDNELs. The overlap with REACH Registrants’ wDNELs ranges from 9 to 39 substances. There is a large variability in ratios between OELs and registrants’ wDNELs, from nearly 100 times lower to nearly 10,000 times higher. The extreme differences on the higher end are in fact instances of registrant’s setting derived minimal effect levels, i.e. a wDMEL rather than wDNEL, hence assuming a non-threshold carcinogenic effect, while the OELs in question are based on a threshold assumption. On average the OELs seem to be somewhat higher than registrants’ wDNELs for this group of substances, with the exception for ECHA RAC OEL recommendations.

In Fig. 2 the OELs and wDNELs are compared to the EU BOELVs showing that all actors have taken the opportunity to set lower values for certain substances (for instance lead). The instances of ratios exceeding 1 are due to the inclusion of not fully implemented BOELVs, as in some cases the BOELVs in our comparisons do not need to be transposed until a later date.

A summary of the critical effects behind the OELs and wDNELs is given in Table 4. The share of available and/or unique documents differs between the lists, however, it is clear that other types of toxicity than reproductive toxicity are commonly identified as the critical effect. Notably, among the reviewed SCOEL documents, reproductive toxicity, while several times mentioned as a specific concern, in a majority of cases was not the health effect expected at the lowest exposures (Table 4). The wDNELs from RAC on the other hand stand out as mostly having reproductive toxicity as the critical effect, here it should be considered that the classification as a reproductive toxicant is a factor in prioritisation for the Restriction and Authorisation procedures. The differences in fraction of reproductive toxicity as the critical effect is both due to differences in substance coverage and differences in conclusions regarding the critical effect for the same substance.

In Fig. 3 we see a trend of safety margins to the critical effect being higher for wDNELs. Safety margins to the lowest cited reproductive toxicity dose-descriptor are in most cases (>85 %) equal to higher than those for the critical effect. In Fig. 3 there are five cases where the documents’ internal safety margins to reproductive toxicity equalled one or less. Three concern SCOEL documents (lead, bisphenol A and carbon monoxide) and two concern RAC OEL documents (cadmium and lead). In the case of lead, both RAC and SCOEL concluded that a threshold for developmental toxicity cannot be identified. Also, the reproductive dose descriptor used for the safety margin calculation in Fig. 3 is an effect level rather than a NOAEL. In the case of cadmium, RAC concluded that general population studies indicate reproductive toxicity (decreased birth weight) at exposure levels around 1 $\mu\text{g Cd}/\text{g creatinine}$ in urine, corresponding to the biological limit value (BLV) RAC proposed for cadmium. RAC also noted that females in fertile age may absorb more cadmium from food because of their reduced iron status and emphasised the need of minimizing occupational cadmium

Table 2

An overview of protection aims with respect to reproductive toxicity, if available, for the included lists of occupational exposure limit values (OELs) and Derived No-Effect Levels for workers long-term inhalation exposure (wDNEL). Quotes are taken from the referenced methodology documents or OEL descriptions and, if necessary, translated to English by the authors.

List [Reference]	Protection aim	Reproductive toxicity notation ^a
EU BOELV [14,15]	“The European Parliament and the Council shall [...] set out limit values [...] on the basis of the available information, including scientific and technical data, in respect of all those carcinogens, mutagens or reprotoxic substances for which this is possible.”	Threshold or non-threshold reproductive toxicity
RAC OEL [21]	“OELs are established to protect workers from adverse effects on health, as defined by (SCOEL 2017, F3–2), that would arise from exposure to the respective chemical agents.” ^b	No
SCOEL [22]	“The principal intended use [of OELs] is to provide standards or criteria against which actual measured exposure levels in existing workplaces may be compared in order to ensure that, as far as the current state of knowledge permits, control of exposure is adequate to protect the health of the workers (and the health of their offspring, as regards developmental effects that may be caused by chemical agents; notwithstanding special precautionary measures will be taken for pregnant workers).”	No
Registrant’s wDNELs [23]	“DNEL for effects that occur upon repeated exposure shall always be derived. Toxicity studies that give information on these possible ‘long-term’ effects of a substance are: repeated dose toxicity studies, reproductive toxicity studies (including developmental toxicity studies), and carcinogenicity studies.”	No
RAC wDNELs [23]	For DNELs in general, the REACH R.8 guidance applies (see above).	No
Finland [24]	“In general, when staying below the OEL, the exposure does not cause harm or danger to the safety or health of employees, or for their reproductive health, in the light of the existing information.”	No
France [25]	“ Limitations of the OEL /.../ The notion of limit value admits the existence of nuisance in the workplace. In this context, certain people are particularly sensitive due to their physiological state (pregnancy, illness, etc.) to the development of an abnormal response (genes at levels considered low, revelation or induction of a pathological state) and are likely not to be protected by the OEL.”	Classification according to CLP criteria.
Netherlands [26]	“A health-based OEL is an exposure level below which no or almost no significant adverse effects are expected in the course of and after working life, or in workers’ offspring”	Classification and labelling proposals according to CLP categories for reproduction toxic substances are prepared by the Subcommittee on the Classification of Substances Toxic to Reproduction.
Latvia [27,28]	“The occupational exposure limit value (OELV) has been determined - such concentration of chemical substances or mixtures in the air of the work environment which for the whole duration of the life of an employee does not cause the contraction of a disease or deterioration of health...”	Classification according to CLP criteria.
Lithuania [29]	“The limit values of chemicals (OELs) are established on the principle that most workers can work under these conditions without experiencing health effects from the chemical.”	R – Toxic to reproduction
MAK Commission [30]	“The sole object of the Commission’s work is to protect, as far as possible and necessary, and in line with the most up to date scientific information, the health of workers and of their offspring.” “Observance of the MAK values and BAT values does not guarantee, in every case, that the unborn child is reliably protected because numerous substances have not yet been investigated or have been only partially tested for prenatal toxicity.”	Pregnancy risk groups Group A: Damage to the embryo or foetus in humans has been unequivocally demonstrated and is to be expected even when the OELs are observed. B: According to currently available information damage to the embryo or foetus cannot be excluded after exposure to concentrations at the level of the OEL. C: Damage to the embryo or foetus is unlikely when the OEL is observed. D: Insufficient data -: Substances without a recommendation R – Toxic to reproduction
Norway [31]	The committee “shall assess the quality of toxicological data and make an assessment that can contain the following points: • a summary of relevant effects, including /.../ reproductive toxicity...”	
Spain [32]	“The Occupational Exposure Limits cannot be assumed to be an adequate assessment criterion to evaluate the risk of exposure to chemical agents of a pregnant or breastfeeding worker. The limit values are established based on a specific critical effect, which does not have to be the risk to pregnancy or breastfeeding.”	TR1 – toxic to human reproduction TR1A (human evidence) TR1B (animal evidence)
Sweden [33]	“The purpose of these provisions [that list OELs, authors’ note] is to prevent ill health in workers as a result of exposure to the substances listed herein.”	R – Substances that can cause harmful effects on fertility or the development of the offspring

^a Excluding listing harmonised classification and labelling outcomes. Note that the EU (2002) update regarding e.g. threshold and non-threshold notifications was not implemented nationally at the time of data compilation for this study.

^b F3–2 does not specifically mention offspring, but “indicating a hazardous property that may potentially be relevant for workers”.

exposure. In the case of bisphenol A, the lowest safety margin for reproductive toxicity in Fig. 3, the dose-descriptor behind the low safety margin is taken from an epidemiological study which SCOEL discussed potentially including a selection bias and other confounding occupational exposures. In the case of carbon monoxide, SCOEL specifically stated at the level of their OEL recommendation, reproductive toxicity cannot be ruled out.

4. Discussion

While the approach to reproductive toxicity differs somewhat between the OEL setters in our selection none explicitly exclude reproductive toxicity from the protective aims, rather the difference lies in how explicit and transparent the acknowledgement of the difficulties of assessing reproductive toxicity is stated. While there are some lists that

Table 3

Comparison of the lists' coverage of substances with a harmonised classification as Reproductive toxicant (Repro) 1 A or 1B, with and without nickel-, chromium (VI)-, cobalt and lead compounds.

List	Including all classified substances		Excluding multiples of metal compounds ^a	
	n _{OEL} for Repro 1 A/B	% of Repro 1 A/B	n _{OEL} for Repro 1 A/B	% of Repro 1 A/B
EU BOELV	95	36 %	16	9 %
RAC OEL rec	35 ^b	11 %	3	2 %
SCOEL rec	49 ^b	18 %	16	9 %
RAC wDNEL	18	7 %	11	6 %
Registrants' wDNELs	93	35 %	72	40 %
Finland	71	27 %	29	16 %
France	36	13 %	20	11 %
Latvia	73	27 %	24	13 %
Lithuania	61	23 %	22	12 %
MAK Commission	31 ^b	12 %	26	15 %
Netherlands	23	9 %	14	8 %
Norway	69	26 %	15	8 %
Spain	42	16 %	26	15 %
Sweden	106	40 %	22	12 %
At least one list	181	68 %	97	53 %

^a Specifically compounds containing Ni (n=59), Cr (VI) (n=8), Co (n=6), Pb (n=10).

^b In some cases additional substances have been assessed by the expert group but no numerical OEL recommendation made, for instance ECHA RAC (n=1 additional), SCOEL (n=7) and MAK commission (n=77), including metal and metal compounds.

^c The number of BOELVs is sometimes higher than individual countries, this is due to inclusion of BOELVs that do not need to be transposed until a later date.

allow socio-economic considerations to play a role, at least for non-threshold carcinogens, previous research has shown that feasibility considerations do not seem to systematically result in higher OELs [34]. Hence, we have no reason to expect the coverage of reproductive

toxicants or safety margin to reproductive toxicity to differ significantly between the included actors. In the present work we have used the harmonized CLP classifications as a starting point to investigate the coverage of reproductive toxicants and safety margins to reproductive

Fig. 1. Comparison of occupational exposure limits (OEL) and RAC derived no-effect levels for workers' long-term inhalation exposure (wDNEL) to registrants' wDNELs for substances with a harmonised classification as Reproductive toxicant 1 A or 1B. The lines indicate the geometric means and their 95 % confidence intervals.

Fig. 2. Comparison of occupational exposure limits (OEL) and Registrants' derived no-effect levels for workers' long-term inhalation exposure (wDNEL) to EU level binding OELs (EU BOELV) for substances with a harmonised classification as Reproductive toxicant 1 A or 1B. The lines indicate the geometric means and their 95 % confidence intervals. RAC wDNELs excluded due to few overlapping substances.

Table 4

Comparison of categories of critical effects across OELs and wDNELs for substances with a harmonised classification as Reproductive toxicant 1 A or 1B and for which scientific documentation was available.^a

Category of toxicity determined as critical effect ^b :					
List	n ^a _{Doc}	Reproductive	Carcinogenicity	Other systemic	Local
RAC OEL rec	7	-	-	29 %	71 %
SCOEL rec	15	14 %	7 %	40 %	40 %
Registrants' wDNELs	76	30 %	16 %	43 %	11 %
RAC wDNELs	11	82 %	9 %	9 %	-
Finland	16	13 %	31 %	31 %	25 %
France	6	50 %	17 %	33 %	0 %
Latvia	-	-	-	-	-
Lithuania	-	-	-	-	-
MAK Commission ^d	41	10 %	29 %	41 %	20 %
Netherlands	7	29 %	42 %	14 %	14 %
Norway	15	60 %	7 %	13 %	20 %
Spain	10	40 %	0 %	30 %	30 %
Sweden	16	6 %	31 %	56 %	6 %

^a Not all scientific documents underlying the OELs were available. The table also excludes instances where other OEL documents already covered by the table (such as the SCOEL recommendation) were adopted by the EU member state or REACH registrant. Furthermore, the number of documents is lower than the number of OELs and wDNELs, as documents were only included once for the same critical effect and key study make up the basis for the full group (e.g. metal compounds).

^b Sum not equal 100 % due to rounding of the values

^c EU BOELVs are not listed separately as they are a subset of SCOEL recommendations.

^d Includes 15 documents for substances that were not assigned any numerical value, e.g., due to non-threshold effects. For the 26 substances with numerical values, 15 are categorised in pregnancy risk group B (effects may not be excluded at OEL), 8 in group C (effects unlikely at OEL) and 3 in D (data insufficient), see also [Table 2](#).

Fig. 3. Comparison of the safety margins to critical effect for OELs and wDNELs to each document's internal safety margin for reproductive toxicity. Substances where safety margins could not be calculated for either critical effect or reproductive toxicity (due to lack of transparency or non-threshold carcinogenicity) are excluded. Note the logarithmic scale and differing ranges on X- vs Y-axis.

toxicity. Our data show that a large number of reproductive toxicants are not covered by current OELs or wDNELs, which to some extent is expected as a harmonized classification as a reproductive toxicant may correlate with reduced commercial use of the substance. Also, not all substances relevant to assess under CLP may have an extensive occupational use, which is a factor in prioritizing a substance for OEL evaluation.

Several works have compared the levels of wDNELs to OELs [35,19,36,37] showing that wDNELs can differ widely from OELs for the same substance, being both lower and higher. In the present work the span ranged from wDNELs being 8 times higher to 7500 times lower. In other words, wDNELs deviate more markedly towards being lower than OELs. Also, the geometric mean of the ratios shows that OELs, with the exception of the ECHA RAC recommendations, tend to be on average somewhat higher than wDNELs. In other comparisons, the range has been less skewed. Schenk & Johanson [19] comparing five sets of OEL recommendations to wDNELs found the range to span from wDNELs being 1000 times lower to nearly 10,000 times higher, also the geometric means were all close to 1 in these comparisons. Hence, our data shows a small tendency for wDNELs, on average, being lower for reproductive toxicants than OELs. However, the variation in levels is still striking.

Overall, it could be expected that wDNELs are lower than OELs for the corresponding substances. First, wDNELs are all relatively recent as the first registration deadline for substances already on the market was in 2010 and the most recent in 2018. Previous research on OEL-setting has indicated that selection of key study and point of departure are

important factors explaining differences in OELs for the same substance, often connected to time of assessment, i.e., access to newer data showing effects at lower doses [38]. Additionally, ECHA's REACH guidance document has introduced a more systematic as well as rigid application of default assessment factors for DNEL derivation compared to practice in general OEL setting [19,39]. That the RAC OELs are among the lowest in the range reflects the same factors, as RAC only started deriving OELs recently and follow the REACH guidance regarding for instance the selection of assessment factors. While lower in numbers, the more consistently low level of RAC OELs could be due to the same expert group deriving the values, and thus a more consistent application of the framework, rather than different actors for each substance as in the case for Registrants' wDNELs.

Classification as a reproductive toxicant means that the substance has the intrinsic property to cause an adverse effect on reproduction or development, but it does not mean that reproductive toxicity is the most sensitive endpoint (as in occurring at the lowest doses) for that substance. Indeed, a simple scrutiny of the safety margins in documents from ECHA RAC, SCOEL and REACH registrants indicate that a majority of safety margins are higher to reproductive toxicity than the critical effect. In a few cases the low safety margins to cited reproductive toxicity data was very low (≤ 1), in these cases there were explicit statements in documents that reproductive toxicity could not be excluded or that the data in question was not considered reliable. Our analysis does not take into consideration that more data on reproductive toxicity may be available, potentially including more conservative dose-descriptors of reliable quality, for the different substances. Study design

is crucial for efficient and reliable identification of reproductive toxicants, and as pointed out by Hellsten et al. [40] in many cases reproductive toxicity studies have had design flaws hampering their use for classification purposes. In fact, given that the difference in numerical values of wDNELs compared to SCOEL and RAC OEL recommendations (Fig. 1) is smaller than that for safety margins (Fig. 3), selection of the point of departure seems to, at least partially, counteract the effect of the higher safety margins of wDNELs. Hence, a full analysis of whether reproductive toxicity is given sufficient consideration would require a comparison to a systematic data collection of quality evaluated data to assess whether cited data are representative of the current state of knowledge on reproductive toxicity.

There are additional challenges to assessing risks of reproductive toxicity, lack of appropriate data may be a factor hampering the identification and dose-response assessment of reproductive toxicity. While the REACH Regulation defines information requirements for registrants to identify the potential reproductive toxicity in a tiered approach depending on the annual tonnage band, it has been pointed out that the requirements for low tonnage substances (<10 ton per annum) may be insufficient for accurate classification and assessment of risk [41]. It has also been pointed out that suitable tests for certain endpoints are missing, in particular mediated through disruption of modalities other than the estrogenic, androgenic, thyroid, and steroidogenesis (EATS) modalities [42]. Furthermore, the risk assessment procedure, such as default assessment factors, may need additional consideration. While safety margins seem to be larger for reproductive toxicity at large in our study, it is a fact that the physiological changes during pregnancy may affect the toxicokinetic parameters underlying our default assumptions for exposure limit derivation, at least for targeting the developing foetus.

5. Conclusions

Far from all substances with a harmonised classification as reproductive toxicant 1 A or 1B have EU level or national OELs, or wDNELs under REACH. However, as possibly expected due to the REACH requirements being triggered by tonnage, the wDNELs cover a larger share of these substance, if counting metal compounds as single entries. Nevertheless, neither the REACH or occupational health and safety legal frameworks supply wDNELs or OELs for a substantial share of known reproductive toxicants. Albeit the REACH registrants' wDNELs on average are lower than corresponding OELs for this selection of reproductive toxicants, the variation is huge. We can thus not conclude that wDNELs consistently offer a larger margin of safety.

The extent to which reproductive toxicity is identified as the critical effect varies between the examined lists. Reviewing the internal margin of safety to cited reproductive toxicity endpoints, we found that based on data cited in documents, safety margins in a majority of cases were larger to reproductive toxicity than the critical effect (when different). This would indicate that concerns for disregard of reproductive toxicity in OEL setting are unwarranted. However, selection of data and thus potential points of departure may explain larger differences than differences in safety margins or assessment factors.

To summarise, wDNELs offer both complementary and conflicting exposure guidelines for reproductive toxicity compared to our selected lists of OELs. BOELVs in turn cover among the fewest substances in the range, and in many cases national OELs or wDNELs are set at more conservative levels. Indications are that reproductive toxicity is not necessarily the most sensitive endpoint in all cases, however, further study on all available data on a substance-by-substance basis as well as an evaluation of suitable safety margins for reproductive toxicity is required to corroborate such a conclusion. In the meantime, while the CMRD not yet has led to increased coverage of reproductive toxicant or consistently increases safety margins, its requirement to primarily substitute, secondarily enclose or if not possible otherwise minimise exposure or risk, remains a sound strategy.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Inese Martinsons: Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Mimmi Leite:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Pasi Huuskonen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Piia Taxell:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Meng-Rung Ho:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Linda Schenk:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Loreta Strumylaite:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Linda Paegle:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Karl-Christian Nordby:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Linda Schenk, Piia Taxell Pasi Huuskonen, Mimmi Leite, Inese Martinsons, Karl-Christian Nordby, Linda Paegle, and Loreta Strumylaite report financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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